

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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ORGANIZATION OF CONTROL AND EVALUATION OF EFFECTIVENESS IN INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES

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Abstract: This article investigates the scientific, theoretical, and methodological foundations for organizing control and evaluating its effectiveness in international companies. By tackling both theoretical and practical issues related to this topic, the study has developed scientific and practical recommendations for the organization of control and assessment of its effectiveness at the joint enterprise UZTEX TASHKENT LLC, which is the subject of this research.

Key words: Transnational companies, backbone factor, globalization, intensification, protectionism.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola xalqaro kompaniyalarda nazoratni tashkil etish va uning samaradorligini baholashning ilmiy, nazariy va uslubiy asoslarini o'rganadi. Mazkur mavzuga oid ham nazariy, ham amaliy masalalarni hal etish orqali tadqiqot ob'ekti bo'lgan "UZTEX TOSHKENT" MChJ qo'shma korxonasida nazoratni tashkil etish va uning samaradorligini baholash bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Transmilliy kompaniyalar, magistral omil, globallashuv, kuchayish, protektsionizm.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются научно-теоретические и методические основы организации контроля и оценки его эффективности в международных компаниях. Решая как теоретические, так и практические вопросы, связанные с данной темой, в ходе исследования были разработаны научно-практические рекомендации по организации контроля и оценке его эффективности на совместном предприятии ООО «UZTEX TASHKENT», являющемся предметом данного исследования.

Ключевые слова: Транснациональные компании, системообразующий фактор, глобализация, интенсификация, протекционизм.

INTRODUCTION

Creating an effective control system during the technological modernization and technical re-equipment of production is a highly complex challenge. Control is implemented at all management levels: corporate, divisional, functional, and individual. It involves a crucial task of assessing both the quantitative and qualitative outcomes of the enterprise's performance. This process includes a feedback system aimed at ensuring the organization meets its established goals.

Control encompasses various activities such as setting standards and benchmarks, analyzing system inputs, comparing results against regulatory norms, identifying deviations and acceptable limits, and ultimately measuring outcomes.

In light of the economic modernization, the government of Uzbekistan continuously emphasizes the importance of developing an effective control system during the technological modernization and technical re-equipment of production. Establishing such a system is vital for driving economic growth and enhancing production capabilities.

To foster economic growth, it is essential to implement an effective control system throughout the technological modernization and re-equipment processes in the real sectors of the economy. Thus, addressing the establishment of an effective control system during this period is a pressing issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The work by R. Antony and V. Govindarajan[1] covers a wide range of principles and methods of management control at the corporate level. The authors emphasize, in particular, the need to assess performance by combining financial and non-financial indicators in international companies. The book presents the main approaches to establishing high-quality control through strategic planning, budgeting, employee performance appraisal and management accounting. In international corporations, it describes in detail the methods of rapid analysis of indicators across branches or departments and their harmonization in a single system. The book by R. Kaplan and D. Norton[2] discusses the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) methodology and its role in strategic management. In the process of assessing control and performance in international companies, the BSC combines key performance indicators (KPIs) in four directions: financial, customer, internal processes and learning and growth. The authors show that this method also allows for the establishment of operational control for transnational corporations, linking the results of activities in branches to the overall strategy.

D. Otley[3] studies the theoretical foundations of scientific research on control and performance assessment. This article deeply analyzes the main elements of management control systems that can be used in international companies - goal setting, resource allocation, performance indicators, incentives and motivation of behavior. The author also notes that control systems should be adapted in accordance with the organization's strategy. The coherence and interaction of control systems in international branches is one of the most important aspects covered in this article.

K. Merchant and W. Van der Stede[4] broadly cover modern concepts of management control systems, in particular, incentives and motivation, accurate measurement of performance results, employee accountability, and control measures organized to achieve strategic goals. It is shown that there may be various cultural and legal differences in international companies, which necessitates the formation of flexible and transparent control mechanisms. Practical steps such as inter-branch benchmarking, internal audit and harmonization with external standards are also described.

In the work of R. Simons[5], management control is analyzed within the framework of the "four levers" (belief systems, boundary systems, diagnostic control systems, interactive control systems). It is emphasized that in order to establish an effective control system in international business, it is important to clearly define certain strategic "boundaries" (boundary systems), to focus on stimulating innovative projects and creativity, and at the same time to conduct interactive control processes quarterly or continuously.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research work, methods widely used in scientific research methodology were used. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods were widely used, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, and in analysis, synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Ensuring the further processing of cotton raw materials in various sectors of the textile and light industry, as well as exporting finished products like dyed yarn, knitted fabric, and textiles to foreign markets, can lead to significant efficiency gains in the production of finished textile goods through the active adoption of modern technologies and design practices. This example highlights that there are numerous untapped resources and opportunities within our country.

The "Uztoqimaliksanoat" association outlines the responsibilities, obligations, and rights of the Department of Strategic Perspectives and Coordination of Scientific Research, based on the directives established in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF 5285 dated December 14, 2017. This department is an independent structural unit of the "Uztogmachilik sanoat" association.

The head of the company serves as the immediate supervisor of all staff members. When adhering to current laws, the leader has the authority to determine wages, grant financial incentives or impose fines on workers, and issue orders. These orders are mandatory for all employees of the enterprise.

The supply and sales department reports directly to the deputy head. In matters pertaining to supply and sales, this department does not report directly to the manager; instead, the deputy manager and the chief engineer oversee the operation of equipment and technological processes in the main and auxiliary workshops.

Management functions at the joint venture UZTEX TASHKENT LLC are centralized under the company head, with all subordinate managers and production units reporting to him. Each manager is responsible for the activities of their assigned departments, exercising sole leadership and making independent decisions.

Subordinate employees are required to follow the directives of their immediate supervisors, and higher-ranking employees should not be approached directly by subordinates.

All employees of UZTEX TASHKENT LLC are hired based on an employment contract with the manager. The head of the company is the direct supervisor of the entire staff and, in accordance with the law, has the authority to manage wages, incentives, and penalties, as well as to issue binding orders.

In the organization, the deputy head of financial affairs collaborates with the head and other deputies on various issues, demonstrating the benefits of teamwork. General meetings of the association involve all participants in decision-making regarding the organization's activities, and the head of management can be elected during these meetings. According to the association's charter, participants' shares are calculated and distributed, and a commission is elected to audit the association's activities, with regular reports presented.

The objectives of analyzing the financial situation of the joint venture UZTEX TASHKENT LLC include evaluating the implementation of the financial plan, assessing the correct or incorrect allocation and utilization of funds, determining the availability of the company's own resources, and ensuring that the working capital reserves align with established plans and accounting practices. This analysis also involves examining the use of bank loans and the overall solvency of the enterprise, alongside studying the circulation of working capital.

In the context of economic modernization, having adequate working capital is essential for the enterprise's operations. A lower consumption of raw materials, supplies, fuel, and energy per unit of output—without compromising product quality leads to reduced product costs, less working capital expenditure, and greater efficiency in resource utilization.

In addition, distribution planning plays a major role in determining the need for working capital in the production and non-production sectors of the enterprise (table 1).

Table 1. Analysis of the economic indicators of the joint venture UZTEX TASHKENT LLC in 2017-2019.

No	Indicators	Unit of measure	2017	2018	2019
1.	Product production capacity	thousand soums	151200,0	198720,0	237910,0
2.	Products sold	thousand soums	145678,0	178910,0	214567,0
3.	Production cost of the product	thousand soums	125672,3	156768,9	198674,5
4.	Profit before tax	thousand soums	94567,9	98678,9	100456,7
5.	Net profit	thousand soums	75654,3	78943,1	80365,4
6.	Value of fixed assets	thousand soums	98867,0	98867,0	100567,7
7.	Capital investments	million soums	45367,0	48767,5	51234,6
8.	Number of employees	person	30	32	35
	including industrial production workers	person	25	27	30
9.	Average salary	thousand soums	280,0	345,0	457,0

The primary focus of economic analysis is to identify opportunities for increasing efficiency within farms, their sectors, and structural departments by applying economic principles and determining effective methods for utilizing these opportunities.

Analyzing the financial situation of the enterprise involves evaluating the implementation of the financial plan, assessing the proper or improper allocation and use of funds, determining whether the company has adequate internal funding, and ensuring that the working capital reserves align with established plans and accounting standards. It also includes analyzing the use of bank loans and evaluating the company's solvency while studying the circulation of working capital (table 2).

Table 2. "Analysis of product production and sales in 2017-2019 at the joint venture UZTEX TASHKENT LLC.

No	Indicators	Unit of measure	2017	2018	2019
1.	Product production capacity	thousand soums	151200,0	198720,0	237910,0
2.	Consumer goods	thousand soums	151200,0	198720,0	237910,0
3.	Volume of realized products	thousand soums	145678,0	178910,0	214567,0
4.	Stocks of finished goods	million soums	5522,0	19810,0	23343,0

As indicated in Table 2, the volume of product production was 151,200.0 thousand soums in 2017, rising to 237,910.0 thousand soums in 2019. The balance sheet serves as the primary source for financial analysis, supplemented by data from financial plans and current accounts.

This represents an increase of 4.0%, amounting to 10,200,000 soums. However, the company's gross profit plan was not fully met, falling short by 8.6 percent.

Table 2 presents an analysis of production and sales at the joint venture UZTEX TASHKENT LLC from 2017 to 2019. The data shows that in 2019, compared to 2018, the volume of product production increased by 157.3%, and the volume of consumer goods sold rose by 147.2% (table 3).

Table 3. Analysis of production costs of the joint venture UZTEX TASHKENT LLC in 2019.

№	Indicators	Unit of measure	According to the plan	The truth	Implementation of the plan, percentage
1.	Product production capacity	thousand soums	213457,8	237910,0	111,4
2.	Total production costs	thousand soums	204323,5	219674,5	107,5
3.	Production cost	thousand soums	185067,9	198674,5	107,0
4.	Necessary benefit	thousand soums	19255,6	21000,0	109,0
5.	Period costs	thousand soums	19255,6	21006,0	109,1

In analyzing the level of profitability, the primary tasks include identifying and studying the key factors that influence profitability. The objectives of analyzing the financial condition of the enterprise focus on using working capital levels to assess the implementation of the financial plan, the appropriate distribution and use of funds, and the level of self-sufficiency. A key purpose of examining compliance with plans, accounting discipline, and the use of bank loans is to uncover shortcomings in the enterprise's financial activities and explore opportunities for more effective fund utilization.

The financial ratios of UZTEX TASHKENT LLC for the years 2017-2019 are presented in Table 2. The solvency ratio and the ratio of equity to debt funds exceeded established norms, while the financial independence and capacity utilization ratios remained at standard levels, indicating that the enterprise is financially stable.

From the data in Table 3, the planned volume of product production was set at 213,457.8 thousand soums, but the actual figure reached 237,910.0 thousand soums, exceeding the plan by 24,452.2 thousand soums, or 111.4 percent. The total production costs plan was fulfilled at 107.5 percent, and the production cost plan was met at 107.3 percent. The required profit was also achieved at 109.0 percent compared to the plan.

It is important to note that the cost of produced goods is a critical indicator of operational efficiency. This metric reflects the effectiveness of expense management, labor productivity, wages, and the utilization of fixed assets and raw materials. The economic report of the enterprise plays a vital role in assessing product costs during operations.

The company's strategy in recent years has focused on further saturating the consumer market and enhancing public welfare. An analysis of the socio-economic indicators reveals that the enterprise has successfully created new jobs due to extensive modernization efforts undertaken.

UZTEX TASHKENT LLC plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of the control system and strengthening the economic potential of the enterprise. The growth rate of production efficiency serves as a key indicator of the progressiveness of the management system implemented. Consequently, the degree to which the enterprise approaches its short-term goals and utilizes production resources effectively can be directly measured as a reflection of management efficiency.

In the context of current market conditions, the management system must prioritize the stability of the enterprise, minimize economic risks, and support the production of high-quality, competitive products.

This chapter focuses on the organization of control within UZTEX TASHKENT LLC. It includes an analysis of the joint enterprise's activities, an evaluation of social and economic indicators that assess its performance, an examination of the obsolescence of the main assets, and an assessment of their condition and repair. Additionally, control methods are elaborated upon to ensure effective management and operational success.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Effective organization of control and performance evaluation systems in international companies is of great importance, especially in the context of globalization, in achieving corporate goals and maintaining competitiveness. In this process, internal control mechanisms, ensuring rational use of resources and methods

for evaluating employee performance should be implemented in a coordinated manner. As a result, it will be possible to introduce clear and measurable indicators that are inextricably linked to strategic planning throughout the organization. Cooperation between different departments, innovative approaches and systematic control practices in accordance with international standards will serve as an important factor.

In order to further improve control and efficiency, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Introduction of an integrated performance indicator system: It is necessary to develop a comprehensive assessment methodology that includes financial and non-financial indicators and is consistent with strategic goals.

2. Widespread use of digital technologies: It is preferable to use the help of advanced information systems to analyze data in real time, monitor employee activities online, and optimize resource consumption.

3. Staff training: It is necessary to organize monitoring and evaluation processes in a consistent and impartial manner, in particular, supported by international certification programs and training.

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